

Synthesis of Certain Schiff's Bases Derived from 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and 1,3,5, Triazines

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In course of our attempts to synthesise different types of derivatives from some 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 1,3,5-triazines for possible use in therapeutics, because of their pharmacological activities^{1,2}, some Schiff's bases possessing these units and the characteristic R-CH = N-R linkage have been prepared. The present communication gives the preparation of these compounds.

The Schiff's bases have been prepared by condensation of 2-amino 5-substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles³ and 2-amino 4-substituted 1,3,5-triazines⁴ with appropriate aldehydes in presence of ethanol⁵.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
						Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	180	70	C ₁₅ N ₃ OH ₁₁	16.23	16.87
2.	„	<i>p</i> -anisyl	200	60	C ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ H ₁₃	14.80	15.05
3.	„	Furfuryl	210	43	C ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ H ₉	17.01	17.57
4.	„	Cinnamyl	218	55	C ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ H ₁₃	14.98	15.27
5.	<i>p</i> -anisyl	Phenyl	235	55	C ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ H ₁₃	14.85	15.05
6.	„	<i>p</i> -anisyl	216	63	C ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ H ₁₅	13.26	13.59
7.	„	Furfuryl	212	25	C ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ H ₁₁	15.42	15.61
8.	„	Cinnamyl	208	36	C ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ H ₁₅	13.52	13.77

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2. *Chem. Abst.*, 1966, **64**, 3573, 5106.
3. *Chem. Abst.*, 1966, **64**, 9737.
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TABLE II

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	% Nitrogen	
						Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	235	68	C ₁₆ N ₅ H ₁₃	25.01	25.46
2.	„	<i>p</i> -anisyl	239	60	C ₁₇ N ₅ OH ₁₅	22.14	22.95
3.	„	Furfuryl	222	40	C ₁₄ N ₅ OH ₁₁	26.13	26.42
4.	„	Cinnamyl	241	42	C ₁₈ N ₅ H ₁₅	23.12	23.26
5.	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	phenyl	139	62	C ₁₆ N ₅ ClH ₁₂	23.15	22.61
6.	„	<i>p</i> -anisyl	124	60	C ₁₇ N ₅ ClOH ₁₄	20.10	20.62
7.	„	Furfuryl	140	45	C ₁₄ N ₅ ClOH ₁₀	24.11	23.37
8.	„	Cinnamyl	167(d)	50	C ₁₈ N ₅ ClH ₁₄	20.19	20.86

(d) denotes decomposition.

The results of the pharmacological tests will be published in due course.

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